

EXPLORING THE COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF ENGLISH TEACHERS IN THE ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM OF TAGUM CITY: A QUALITATIVE INQUIRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18638063>

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this descriptive qualitative research was to examine the communication strategies utilized by English teachers in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in the Division of Tagum City. Using purposive sampling, 14 ALS teachers participated in the study, with seven who underwent in-depth interviews and another seven who took part in the focus group discussion. Utilizing thematic analysis to examine the gathered data, the findings revealed that English teachers employed a range of adaptive communication strategies, including code-switching and mother-tongue use, visual and non-verbal cues, real-life contextualization, peer-supported interaction, and learner-centered practices aimed at building comprehension and confidence. However, the teachers also encountered persistent challenges such as limited instructional resources, highly diverse learner profiles, and learners' low confidence and fear of making mistakes when using English. Additionally, the results of the study offer immense significance to ALS English teachers, ALS learners, program administrators, DepEd officials, and future researchers, as they provide foundational research-based evidence and understanding on the use of communication strategies in non-formal learning contexts and inform the development of responsive, learner-centered, and context-sensitive approaches that enhance engagement, build confidence, and improve the overall quality of English instruction in the Alternative Learning System.

Keywords: *communication strategies; Alternative Learning System; ALS teachers; Tagum City, Philippines; descriptive qualitative inquiry*

INTRODUCTION

Effective communication is paramount in the language classroom, but teachers often face difficulty in sustaining communication due to the students' reluctance to communicate and poor communication skills. Despite employing various communication strategies, which are organized plans that aim to effectively communicate messages to a specific group, the teacher's initiative still falls short when their students prefer not to engage in oral discussions. Evidently, this problem is particularly glaring in English as a Second Language (ESL) classes, where language barriers and cultural differences can further exacerbate the problem (Rahman & Razali, 2024). The lack of student participation hampers the learning process the most and limits the teacher's effectiveness in giving feedback to the students.

Issues in eliciting communication among students are a global challenge faced by ESL teachers. In Kenya, a survey of secondary school teachers indicated that their students encountered communication issues due to difficulty pronouncing specific English terms, unequal engagement in the classroom, and reticence for explanation or raising concerns from their teachers (Kabellow et al., 2020). Furthermore, in Malaysia, teachers shared that students are reluctant to engage in class discussions due to fear of making mistakes in communicating their ideas (Rahman & Razali, 2024). They further found that this fear of communication is due to their lack of confidence in using the English language. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, secondary school teachers disclosed that they observed their students' hesitancy to communicate with their teachers and their classmates in English due to the latter's lack of vocabulary and lack of confidence when speaking the English language (Purwati et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, a study among secondary ESL students within the Division of Bataan revealed that a portion of the student population has subpar oral and written communication skills due to poor vocabulary and a lack of practice of the language outside of the classroom (Separa et al., 2020). This makes it hard for teachers to communicate with their students in a second language. Additionally, high school teachers in Negros Oriental reported that employment of communication strategies was especially difficult during the pandemic, as students showed a lack of motivation to take part in the class and had less-than-ideal communication skills (Abarca, 2024). The study further noted that switching to virtual distance learning during the height of COVID-19 further exacerbated these challenges, as teachers faced difficulties due to the limited opportunities for students to improve their communication skills.

Despite the researcher's comprehensive review of available and accessible literature, there is a dearth of available studies on the communication strategies of ESL teachers conducted within the region. A study on the oral communication skills of high school ESL learners in Lupon revealed low English speech performance skills and high speech apprehension among the students (Sayson 2017, as cited in Baful & Derequito, 2022). This emphasizes the need for ESL teachers to use communication strategies to overcome communication difficulties in the classroom. Furthermore, the study stressed the need for teachers to create a friendly and less threatening learning atmosphere by

employing communicative strategies to encourage more active engagement in communication activities.

Based on these identified problematic circumstances, this study was initiated to explore the communication strategies of ALS English teachers in Tagum City. While numerous studies have examined teaching practices and communication strategies in traditional classroom settings, there remains a gap in the literature specifically focusing on ALS educators. For instance, Bukit et al. (2023) investigated the communication strategies of elementary teachers in Indonesia, recommending further research on teaching strategies across diverse educational frameworks. However, this study did not include ALS or comparable non-traditional programs, which Mehra et al. (2021) described as a non-formal education program primarily targeting out-of-school youth and adult learners throughout the Philippines. Additionally, while research such as Alvarez (2024) provided an overview of the ALS's significance in offering non-mainstream learning to teenagers and adults who are not enrolled in traditional classrooms, it did not delve into the specific communication methods employed by teachers to engage learners effectively. This lack of focus on ALS teachers' strategies underlines the necessity of the current research. Lastly, as highlighted by Catyong et al. (2023), there is a notable gap in research concerning the specific practices and challenges confronting ALS educators in communication.

Given the limited research on communication strategies employed by teachers, which is more pronounced in the context of the Alternative Learning System (ALS), this present research intends to fill this gap by delving into how English teachers in the ALS engage with their students in the unique context of non-formal education. Moreover, this research intends to investigate the various strategies teachers employ to modify their communication techniques in order to address the unique needs, circumstances, and learning settings of ALS students.

This study's findings will improve insights into effective communication strategies used in ALS classrooms, providing practical insights to help teachers navigate the challenges of teaching non-mainstream learners. Furthermore, this research will serve as a foundation for improving teacher training programs and developing more effective pedagogical approaches within ALS. The results will be shared in academic journals and conferences to ensure wider dissemination and application in similar educational settings. For ALS teachers handling English subjects, being strategic in communication is crucial to cater to the needs of their ALS learners, who often encounter unique challenges such as limited vocabulary and low confidence, which can affect their participation and understanding. Through carefully tailored communication strategies, ALS teachers can help bridge these gaps in their students' communication ability, promote active engagement, and make learning English more accessible and effective for their students.

Research Questions

1. What communication strategies are utilized by English teachers of ALS learners in Tagum City?
 - 1.1. As an English teacher, what communication strategies have you employed in teaching ALS learners? How did you implement it? Please expound each strategy.
 - 1.2. How will you describe your experiences in implementing these communication strategies among the ALS learners? Please share more about it.
 - 1.3. How do ALS learners respond to the communication strategies you implemented in your English class?
 - 1.4. How do these communication strategies impact your teaching as an English teacher of ALS learners?
 - 1.5. What challenges have you faced when implementing communication strategies with ALS learners?
 - 1.6. How do you adapt your communication techniques to meet the diverse needs of your ALS learners?
 - 1.7. Can you share a specific instance when a communication strategy was particularly effective in facilitating learning? In what particular way did it become effective?
 - 1.8. How did your experience as an ALS teacher shape your understanding on the role of communication in teaching?
2. What challenges do teachers face when using communication strategies in teaching ALS learners?
 - 2.1. Earlier, you mentioned the challenges you encountered in implementing communication strategies among all learners in your English class. How did you address or cope with these challenges? Please elaborate.
 - 2.2. How do you modify or innovate your teaching methods to overcome communication difficulties in the ALS context?
 - 2.3. What role does collaboration with fellow teachers or stakeholders play in resolving communication-related challenges?
 - 2.4. How do you identify and address language barriers that hinder effective communication in your English class with the ALS learners?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative research design to examine the “what,” “why,” and “how” of ALS teachers’ communication practices in engaging diverse learners (Kyngäs, 2019). Qualitative inquiry is an iterative process that involves the systematic collection and interpretation of non-numerical data to understand social phenomena and human experience (Aspers & Corte, 2019; Nassaji, 2020).

The design enabled an in-depth exploration of how ALS teachers in Tagum City adapt their communication strategies to learners from varied socio-economic and educational backgrounds, identify challenges in instruction, and develop responsive pedagogical practices within the flexible ALS context. Guided by phenomenological sensibilities, the study sought to surface teachers' lived experiences and to generate a contextualized account of communication in alternative education settings.

The study was conducted in Tagum City, Philippines. Specific institutions are not identified to maintain confidentiality and to comply with ethical restrictions.

Fourteen (14) ALS teachers from the Division of Tagum City participated in the study. Seven took part in individual in-depth interviews, and seven joined a focus group discussion. This sample size aligns with recommendations for qualitative inquiry in education and social sciences (Guetterman, 2015).

Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure alignment with the study's objectives (Andrade, 2020; Ames et al., 2019). Inclusion criteria required that participants: (a) handle Junior High School learners in the ALS program; (b) possess at least three years of ALS teaching experience; and (c) teach a minimum of three English subjects within the program.

Primary data were gathered through semi-structured in-depth interviews and focus group discussions (Barrett & Twycross, 2018). A researcher-developed interview guide consisting of open-ended questions addressed: (a) communication strategies in ALS classrooms, (b) instructional challenges, (c) adaptive practices, (d) learner engagement, and (e) contextual constraints.

The instrument underwent expert validation by three specialists in qualitative research and ALS education prior to administration. Secondary sources, including scholarly literature, were consulted to support interpretation.

Following ethical clearance and administrative approval, participants received orientation sessions and signed informed consent forms. Face-to-face interviews were scheduled at participants' convenience and lasted approximately one hour. All sessions were audio-recorded, supplemented with field notes, transcribed verbatim, and securely stored for analysis.

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework: familiarization, coding, theme development, review, definition, and reporting. A color-coding system facilitated pattern identification and theme construction. To enhance analytic rigor, coding and theme generation were reviewed in consultation with a qualitative data analyst, thereby strengthening credibility and trustworthiness.

This study concentrated on the strategies and personal experiences of 14 ALS educators within Tagum City. This study was conducted from January 2025 to January 2026. Moreover, the data of this research were limited only to the responses provided by

the ALS teachers in Tagum City who employ communicative strategies to the ALS students within the study period. In particular, in the focus group discussion, the data was limited to the responses of ALS teachers from seven different schools in the Division of Tagum City.

The limitations of this study encompassed the scope of participants and the nature of data gathering. Since this study made use of purposive sampling of ALS teachers in Tagum City, the generalizability of the findings toward other contexts potentially diminished. Moreover, since the study employed in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with open-ended questions, participants had significant control over their responses, which ultimately affected the objectivity of the data. Furthermore, the researcher maintained objectivity by bracketing personal biases and preconceptions throughout the research process.

RESULTS

Table 1: Communication Strategies Utilized by English Teachers of ALS Learners

Table 1 presents the major themes together with the corresponding core ideas derived from the participants' shared experiences and reflections. The first research question explored, "What communication strategies are utilized by English teachers of ALS learners in Tagum City?" Based on the comprehensive analysis of the participants' narratives gathered through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, several strategies were identified, reflecting the teachers' adaptive methods in facilitating learning within the Alternative Learning System.

After thorough thematic analysis of the gathered responses on the Communication Strategies Utilized by English Teachers of ALS Learners from the division of Tagum City, eight major themes emerged: (1) Code-Switching and Mother Tongue as Comprehension Strategies, (2) Utilizing Visual and Non-Verbal Cues, (3) Contextualizing Learning through Real-life Application, (4) Establishing Safe and Learner-Centered Environments to Build Confidence, (5) Building Confidence and Participation through Communication Strategies, (6) Utilizing Peer Learning to Strengthen Comprehension and Boost Confidence, (7) Enhancing Learning through the Integration of Real-Life Contexts and Practical Examples, and (8) Demonstrating Flexibility and Adaptability in Teaching to Address Diverse Needs of the Learners.

Communication Strategies Utilized by English Teachers of ALS Learners

Table 1
Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Communication Strategies Utilized by English Teachers of ALS Learners

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Using Code-Switching and Mother Tongue as Comprehension Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using code-switching and multiple sensory strategies (visual, auditory, olfactory) to enhance comprehension • Employing code-switching to clarify and deepen understanding of difficult vocabulary • Using the learners' mother tongue (Filipino/Bisaya) alongside English to support comprehension • Integrating code-switching and multi-sensory learning strategies
Utilizing Visual and Non-Verbal Cues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing visual instructional materials to support comprehension • Integrating non-verbal signals to manage interaction and learner attention • Using gestures and physical actions to reinforce meaning
Contextualizing Learning through Real-life Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting topics to learners' daily experiences • Using real-life contexts • Using role-play to simulate real situations
Establishing Safe and Learner-Centered Environments to Build Confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a safe and non-judgmental learning space • Providing encouragement that helps shy learners participate confidently • Building trust through patience and supportive teacher–learner interaction • Recognizing small achievements to strengthen learner confidence

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing learners to gradually gain confidence in a learner-centered environment
Building Learners' Confidence and Participation through Communication Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using code-switching and rephrasing to reduce fear of mistakes and build learners' confidence • Encouraging learners to become more participative and independent by mixing English with their native language • Enhancing language development, lesson interactivity, and confidence in speaking English through communication strategies • Employing simple words, body language, and guiding questions to help learners engage despite limited vocabulary
Using Peer Learning as a Strategy to Support Comprehension and Confidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying the peer or "buddy-buddy" method to improve comprehension through explanations from classmates • Allowing classmates to explain lessons in familiar language (Bisaya), supported by visuals and gestures, to strengthen learner confidence • Facilitating pair and group activities that enable stronger learners to guide others while reducing pressure from the teacher • Pairing advanced learners with struggling peers to promote learner-to-learner interaction and shared understanding
Enhancing Learning through Real-Life Context and Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using real-life context (daily activities, jobs) makes language practice more meaningful • Presenting lessons through simple and real-life examples to enhance understanding and relevance

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making learning more effective, meaningful, and engaging through real-life examples • Integrating role-plays and scenario-based activities to make learning practical and meaningful
<p>Demonstrating Flexibility and Adaptability in Teaching to Address Learners' Diverse Needs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting lesson plans and communication strategies flexibly • Practicing learner-centered flexibility by meeting learners where they are and acknowledging small progress • Addressing instructional challenges through resourcefulness, patience, and adaptation • Recognizing flexibility as essential by responding to different learner needs, languages, and communication styles

In summary, the communication strategies employed by English teachers of ALS learners in Tagum City, as identified through thematic analysis of interview and focus group data addressing the question of what strategies teachers use to engage diverse learners. Eight interrelated themes emerged: code-switching and use of the mother tongue to clarify meaning; use of visual and non-verbal cues; contextualizing lessons through real-life applications; creating safe, learner-centered environments; fostering confidence and participation through supportive communication; employing peer learning to enhance comprehension; integrating practical, real-world examples; and demonstrating flexibility and adaptability to meet varied learner needs. Collectively, these strategies reflect teachers' responsive and learner-centered practices aimed at reducing anxiety, improving understanding, strengthening participation, and addressing linguistic, social, and educational diversity within the ALS classroom.

Table 2: Challenges of English Teachers in Using Communication Strategies for ALS Learners

Table 2 presents the major themes together with their corresponding core ideas drawn from the participants' shared experiences and perspectives. These themes show the challenges confronted by the ALS English teachers when utilizing communication strategies inside their classrooms. the second research question inquired, "What

challenges do teachers face when using communication strategies in teaching ALS learners?” Based on the thorough thematic analysis of the responses gathered from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, several recurring issues were identified that reflect the teachers’ struggles in effectively applying various communication strategies in the Alternative Learning System.

After examining and categorizing the participants’ responses, 3 major themes surfaced: (1) Overcoming Resource Constraints in ALS Instruction, (2) Dealing with the Diversity of Learners, and (3) Managing Low Confidence of the Learners and Fear of Mistakes in Using English.

Table 2
Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Challenges of English Teachers in Using Communication Strategies for ALS Learners

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Experiencing Resource Constraints in ALS Instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dealing with limited materials, requiring improvised teaching and creativity • Experiencing a lack of textbooks and outdated modules, necessitating contextualization • Dealing with intermittent internet access, alongside irregular sessions • Navigating limited resources and inconsistent attendance through flexible strategies
Addressing Challenges in Learner Diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling diverse learner backgrounds (working students, single mothers, IP learners) with varied pace and confidence • Addressing differing levels of learner comprehension, with some requiring repeated explanations • Teaching learners from different grade levels or educational attainment, resulting in learning gaps • Working with learners who have varied educational backgrounds and English proficiency levels
Facing Low Confidence and Fear of Mistakes in Using English	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcoming learners’ fear of making mistakes, leading to silence despite encouragement • Confronting learner shyness and hesitation to practice due to fear of being laughed at

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting learners' lack of confidence in speaking English through the use of mixed languages • Recognizing how past negative experiences (e.g., punishment for mistakes) reinforced fear and low confidence
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Table 2 synthesizes the challenges ALS English teachers encounter when implementing communication strategies, as revealed through thematic analysis of interview and focus group data addressing the second research question on instructional difficulties in ALS contexts. Three dominant themes emerged: resource constraints, learner diversity, and learners' low confidence and fear of making mistakes in English. Teachers reported limited and outdated materials, unreliable internet access, and irregular attendance, which required improvisation and flexible instructional planning.

They also struggled with heterogeneous learner profiles, including varied ages, life circumstances, educational attainment, and English proficiency, often necessitating repeated explanations and differentiated pacing. Additionally, persistent learner anxiety, shyness, and prior negative schooling experiences hindered oral participation, compelling teachers to rely on supportive language practices and confidence-building techniques to sustain engagement and communication in ALS classrooms.

DISCUSSION

The primary purpose of this phenomenological inquiry was to explore and understand the experiences of English teachers in the utilization of communication strategies toward their ALS learners in the Division of Tagum City. In particular, this delves into the strategies they employed in addressing the learning needs of their students, the challenges they encountered in facilitating instruction, and the insights they gained that may inform and guide other ALS teachers or those in similar contexts. Lastly, data were gathered through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions using validated research instruments, all of which provided rich and meaningful responses that served as the basis for analysis.

Communication Strategies Utilized by English Teachers of ALS Learners

Following an in-depth thematic analysis of the participants' responses regarding the communication strategies employed by English teachers of ALS learners in the Division of Tagum City, eight key themes were identified: (1) Using Code-Switching and Mother Tongue as Comprehension Strategies, (2) Utilizing Visual and Non-Verbal Cues, (3) Contextualizing Learning through Real-life Application, (4) Establishing Safe and Learner-Centered Environments to Build Confidence, (5) Building Confidence and Participation through Communication Strategies, (6) Using Peer Learning as a Strategy

to Support Comprehension and Confidence, (7) Enhancing Learning through Real-Life Context and Examples, and (8) Demonstrating Flexibility and Adaptability in Teaching to Address Learners' Diverse Needs.

Using Code-Switching and Mother Tongue as Comprehension Strategies

English teachers handling ALS learners in the Division of Tagum City mostly utilized code-switching and the learners' mother tongue to make lessons more understandable for their learners. Specifically, alternating between the target language, English, and Filipino or Bisaya helps clarify unfamiliar terms and explain concepts that were seen as difficult to understand for some students. For many, this practice was especially useful in accommodating learners of different ages and backgrounds who entered the program with uneven levels of English exposure. Additionally, when code-switching was paired with visual or auditory supports, comprehension became much easier for students to achieve.

This finding supports the view that communication strategies are essentially planned methods for ensuring that messages are received clearly (Chaika, 2020; Goldberg & Gustafson, 2022). In ALS classes, where learners often face significant vocabulary gaps, code-switching acts as a type of achievement strategy, allowing teachers to pursue their lesson objectives without abandoning the communicative goal (Faerch & Kasper, 1980, as cited in Chen & Huang, 2024; Addimando, 2024). Instead of being seen as a weakness, the use of the mother tongue functioned as a bridge that made English instruction less intimidating and more accessible.

Moreover, the participants' responses also point to the interactive role of code-switching, which echoes the idea that communication involves constant negotiation of meaning between speakers and listeners (Bin-Tahir et al., 2020). When the English teachers fluidly utilized English and the learners' native languages, it provided the necessary space for the ALS learners to confirm their understanding and contribute to classroom dialogue more confidently. This practice has been found to relate to interactional strategies that emphasize cooperation and clarification during conversations (Zamani et al., 2022; Yu & Kaur, 2024).

The teachers' deliberate use of Filipino and Bisaya further reflects the adaptive nature of communication strategies in language teaching (Aqida & Mandarani, 2024; Rahman & Isroyana, 2021). In non-formal contexts such as the ALS where exposure to the English language is often limited inside the classroom, using only English as medium of instruction can oftentimes alienate the learners and discourage participation (Putra et al., 2023). Through the use of the ALS learners' mother tongue, the teachers can ensure that learning will remain inclusive, supportive, and responsive to the diverse backgrounds and of the students.

In summary, the responses of the participants highlight how code-switching and the use of the mother tongue address what the reviewed scholars call as "problematicity" or moments when communication difficulties emerge and require adjustment (Abdelkarim

& Alhaj, 2023; Davlataliyeva, 2021). For ALS teachers in Tagum City, code-switching and use of mother tongue served as practical tools that aid in building comprehension, sustaining motivation, and making English instruction more meaningful in a setting that serves learners from all walks of life.

Utilizing Visual and Non-Verbal Cues

Another strategy employed was the visual aids and non-verbal cues to make lessons clearer and easier to grasp. When explanations are paired with gestures, drawings, or even simple actions, students were able to follow the discussion more easily and comprehend ideas that were difficult to explain in words alone. Additionally, for learners who are not confident enough to speak English, these cues and hints served as a form of support, helping them keep up without feeling embarrassed.

Furthermore, several studies have shown the value of using visual and non-verbal cues as communication strategies. Mareza et al. (2021) and Firharmawan et al. (2023) noted that indirect communication strategies, such as gestures or visual signals, do not always fix language gaps directly but still make interaction smoother. In the ALS context, this was evident when learners used the teacher's actions or visuals as a guide for meaning. Instead of relying only on English input, students could connect ideas with concrete images or familiar movements, which made comprehension easier and reduced frustration.

Meanwhile, the responses also reflected what Putra et al. (2023) described as addressing the "exposure gap" in English. Many ALS learners begin the program with very little practice in the language, so teachers need to support their explanations with pictures, charts, or hand signals. These additions were not just helpful for understanding but also made the lessons more accessible to students with different levels of literacy. Teachers further observed that the use of gestures and visuals had an emotional effect on learners. Students often felt reassured when they saw a teacher point, act something out, or show a visual example, because it confirmed that they were following the lesson correctly. This supports the interactional view of communication, where meaning is built not only through words but also through context and shared cues between speakers (Zamani et al., 2022; Yu & Kaur, 2024).

In this way, visuals and non-verbal signals were more than just add-ons to instruction. For ALS English teachers, they were practical tools that made learning less intimidating and more engaging, especially for students who entered the program with limited confidence in using English.

Contextualizing Learning through Real-life Application

The use of real-life contexts makes lessons meaningful and relevant for the ALS students. Furthermore, learners understood better when topics were connected to familiar experiences, such as everyday routines, community situations, or family interactions. Some shared that role-playing based on real-life scenarios encouraged students to

practice English in a way that felt natural and less intimidating. Lastly, drawing on learners' own experiences helped them see the relevance of English to their daily lives.

This finding reflects the view of communication strategies as adaptive tools that support comprehension and active participation (Chen & Huang, 2024; Rahman & Isroyana, 2021). In ALS settings, many learners struggle not only with language gaps but also with finding a reason to engage with academic content. By linking lessons to their lived experiences, teachers addressed what Abdelkarim and Alhaj (2023) describe as "problematicity," or the moment when learners recognize a gap in their understanding. Real-life examples gave students a practical frame of reference, allowing them to bridge this gap more effectively.

The participants' responses also illustrate how contextualization aligns with the interactional approach to communication. When lessons were tied to authentic situations, learners were more willing to negotiate meaning, ask questions, and share their own perspectives. Studies on meaning negotiation highlight that communication improves when learners exchange ideas connected to their own realities (Rachma et al., 2020; Garcia, 2020). In this sense, real-life applications created a classroom atmosphere where interaction was purposeful and grounded in shared experiences.

Moreover, contextualization served not only a cognitive function but also a motivational one. Learners reported that they felt more engaged when they could relate topics to their personal circumstances. This observation is consistent with Putra et al. (2023), who stressed that communication strategies help sustain learners' interest by bridging exposure gaps. In the ALS context, where learners often face irregular attendance or competing responsibilities, the chance to see their own lives reflected in the lesson helped keep them invested in the learning process.

Lastly, the responses of ALS English teachers show that contextualizing lessons through real-life application is not a simple teaching preference but a necessary strategy for this unique learning environment. Through the utilization of authentic contexts in the teaching of English, teachers not only clarified meaning but also validated learners' experiences, making the classroom a space where language learning was both practical and personally relevant.

Establishing Safe and Learner-Centered Environments to Build Confidence

Establishing a safe and supportive environment is a crucial part of ALS teachers' communication strategies. Learners were initially shy and hesitant to participate, especially when speaking in English. Over time, however, as they were assured of patience and encouragement from their teachers, they began to take more risks with the language. Once students felt secure from ridicule or harsh correction, they gradually built confidence and became more active in class discussions.

This finding connects with the idea that communication strategies are not limited to language tactics alone but also include the creation of conditions that support

interaction (Rahman & Isroyana, 2021). By prioritizing patience and emotional safety, teachers reduced the “affective filter” that often prevents learners from fully engaging in communication. In non-formal programs like ALS, where learners may carry insecurities due to past school experiences or long gaps in education, building trust within the learning space becomes a strategy in itself for facilitating comprehension and participation.

The teachers’ experiences also coincide with the findings of Zamani et al. (2022) and Yu and Kaur (2024), who noted that interactional strategies involve cooperation between speakers to achieve shared understanding. In this case, the cooperation was not only linguistic but also relational. Teachers who fostered safe and respectful environments encouraged learners to respond more freely, negotiate meaning, and make mistakes without fear, making communication more authentic and less focused on error avoidance.

Creating a learner-centered space is particularly relevant given the challenges faced by ALS teachers. Francisco and Buri (2024) emphasized that heavy workloads, limited resources, and diverse learner needs often make it difficult to provide individualized support. Against these constraints, the deliberate effort of teachers to ensure patience, empathy, and safety demonstrates how learner-centered environments serve as communication strategies that address both the academic and emotional needs of students.

Overall, the responses illustrate that emotional care and encouragement are integral to effective communication in the ALS classroom. When teachers create an atmosphere of trust and acceptance, learners are more willing to speak, participate, and believe in their ability to succeed. Through this safe and supportive learning space, ALS English teachers not only strengthened language skills but also restored learners’ confidence in their own capacity to learn.

Building Confidence and Participation through Communication Strategies

Meanwhile, another strategy that stood out was the importance of communication strategies in helping learners overcome fear and gradually build confidence in using English. Simple techniques such as code-switching, gestures, synonyms, and rephrasing were effective in reducing learners’ hesitation to speak. Since the ALS learners are provided with multiple ways of expressing their thoughts, these strategies made English less intimidating and allowed students to participate more freely. Learners who were once reluctant eventually started using English, often in combination with their native language, as a practical step toward meaningful communication.

This finding reflects the role of communication strategies as adaptive tools that support learners when vocabulary or grammar knowledge is insufficient (Chen & Huang, 2024; Kan et al., 2024). Instead of avoiding interaction, learners were encouraged to rely on accessible strategies such as rephrasing or mixing languages, which aligns with achievement strategies that maintain communication goals despite linguistic gaps (Faerch & Kasper, 1980, as cited in Chen & Huang, 2024). In ALS classrooms, where

learners have different educational backgrounds and confidence levels, these approaches helped lower the affective barriers that often keep students silent.

Teachers also observed that learners became more participative and independent once they felt secure in trying out English. This supports the idea that communication strategies not only aid comprehension but also strengthen self-expression and interaction (Rahman & Isroyana, 2021). Research on interactional strategies has shown that opportunities to confirm meaning or ask clarification questions promote active engagement (Zamani et al., 2022; Yu & Kaur, 2024). The responses of ALS teachers confirm this, showing that learners gained confidence as they used simple words, gestures, and questions to sustain classroom conversations.

The process of building confidence through these strategies is especially important in the ALS context, where learners often carry insecurities from past educational experiences (Guiamalon et al., 2022; Francisco & Buri, 2024). By using communication strategies that emphasized support rather than correction, teachers created conditions where learners could attempt to speak without fear of mistakes. Over time, this not only improved language development but also made lessons more interactive and motivating. Teachers' responses therefore highlight that confidence in communication is not developed by fluency alone but by consistent encouragement through strategies that make participation possible. When ALS learners were given accessible ways to communicate, they grew more willing to engage, showing that confidence and participation are outcomes of both effective strategies and supportive teaching.

Using Peer Learning as a Strategy to Support Comprehension and Confidence

Peer learning played an important role in supporting both comprehension and confidence among learners. Moreover, the “buddy-buddy” method allowed students to explain lessons to one another in more familiar and accessible ways. Explanations given in Bisaya, often accompanied by gestures or simple visuals, helped struggling learners understand concepts more clearly. For many students, learning from a classmate reduced the pressure they felt when being called on directly by the teacher, making the experience less intimidating and more encouraging.

Furthermore, this finding resonates with the literature on interactional strategies, where communication is seen as a collaborative effort to bridge understanding (Zamani et al., 2022; Yu & Kaur, 2024). In ALS classrooms, peer explanations served as a form of meaning negotiation, as learners actively worked together to clarify ideas and confirm understanding. Such peer-to-peer interaction aligns with Rahman and Isroyana's (2021) assertion that strategies like clarification, repetition, and monitoring interaction enhance both comprehension and participation. When stronger learners guided their peers, communication became more fluid and less hierarchical, helping everyone remain engaged in the lesson.

The use of peer learning also connects to the idea of achievement strategies, where learners find alternative ways to express meaning and overcome language gaps

(Addimando, 2024; Gaddi et al., 2024). Instead of relying solely on the teacher, students provided paraphrases, examples, or translations that bridged comprehension gaps. These exchanges not only improved understanding but also allowed struggling learners to gain confidence in participating. In this way, peer support complemented teacher strategies and created a more learner-centered classroom dynamic.

In the context of ALS, where classes are composed of individuals with varied ages, backgrounds, and levels of English proficiency, peer learning also addressed the challenge of learner diversity. Francisco and Buri (2024) observed that ALS teachers often struggle to balance these differences, and pairing advanced learners with those who needed more support provided a practical way to address this gap. Teachers' responses confirm that peer learning encouraged interaction, distributed responsibility for communication, and created opportunities for learners to develop confidence in using English without fear of judgment.

The responses illustrate that peer learning is more than just a teaching technique; it is a communication strategy that empowers learners to help one another. By working together, ALS students not only improved comprehension but also developed confidence in speaking, showing that supportive peer interaction is a valuable tool in non-formal learning contexts.

Enhancing Learning through Real-Life Context and Examples

Connecting lessons to real-life situations made language learning more meaningful and effective. The learners understood concepts better when activities reflected their daily routines, jobs, or common community interactions. Role-plays and situational tasks, such as acting out a conversation in a store, a job interview, or even composing text messages, helped the ALS learners practice English in ways that were both practical and relatable. When lessons were anchored in familiar experiences, students not only grasped new vocabulary faster but also became more engaged and motivated to participate.

This specific communication strategy, meanwhile, supports the argument that communication strategies are most effective when they connect language learning with authentic contexts (Rahman & Isroyana, 2021; Yulianti, 2024). In ALS classrooms, where learners come from varied life backgrounds, contextualizing lessons through real-life examples allowed teachers to make English instruction relevant and accessible. As Chen and Huang (2024) explained, communicative strategies serve as cognitive tools that help learners bridge gaps in knowledge; in this case, the real-life context served as the scaffold that linked classroom learning to actual experience.

Teachers' use of real-life contexts also aligns with the concept of achievement and interactional strategies, which emphasize maintaining communication and negotiating meaning through relatable situations (Faerch & Kasper, 1980, as cited in Chen & Huang, 2024; Zamani et al., 2022). When learners engaged in role-playing or scenario-based tasks, they were given opportunities to experiment with English freely, using it in natural

exchanges instead of memorized drills. This mirrors the idea of meaning negotiation discussed by Rahman and Isroyana (2021), where interaction becomes more authentic when learners use language to accomplish real purposes.

Moreover, this practice reflects what Putra et al. (2023) identified as the value of bridging exposure gaps in non-formal education. Many ALS learners have limited exposure to English outside the classroom, so connecting language lessons with real-life contexts compensates for this lack of immersion. By designing activities rooted in everyday situations, teachers not only promoted comprehension but also equipped learners with practical communication skills that could be applied beyond the classroom. The responses emphasize that real-life context and examples transformed the ALS classroom into a space where language was lived, not just learned. Through contextualized communication, learners discovered that English could serve a purpose in their daily lives, making learning both relevant and empowering.

Demonstrating Flexibility and Adaptability in Teaching to Address Diverse Needs of the Learners

The final communication strategy emphasized that flexibility and adaptability were vital in addressing the diverse needs of their learners. Each class included students of different ages, backgrounds, and levels of English proficiency, which made a uniform approach to teaching impractical. To address this, teachers constantly adjusted lesson plans, modified activities, and varied their communication styles to suit individual learning paces. For many, flexibility meant meeting learners where they were, recognizing small achievements, and allowing each student to begin from a point of comfort rather than strict academic expectation.

In this regard, Putra et al. (2023) highlighted that communication strategies in language teaching are most effective when tailored to learners' specific contexts and needs. ALS teachers demonstrated this principle by using patience, resourcefulness, and creativity to design lessons that worked even in unpredictable situations. This aligns with Rahman and Isroyana's (2021) view that communicative teaching involves constant adjustment to ensure that messages are understood clearly despite differences in learners' backgrounds. By being flexible, teachers maintained engagement and made learning more inclusive for students who might otherwise have felt left behind.

This adaptability reflects the concept of achievement and interactional strategies described by Faerch and Kasper (1980, as cited in Chen & Huang, 2024) and Zamani et al. (2022). Teachers' willingness to change their methods, switch between languages, or simplify explanations demonstrates how communicative competence in ALS extends beyond linguistic skills to include social and pedagogical responsiveness. Flexibility allowed teachers to maintain communication goals even when faced with learners who had limited exposure to English or irregular attendance.

The importance of flexibility also connects with the challenges identified by Francisco and Buri (2024), who reported that ALS teachers face heavy workloads and

highly diverse learner profiles. In such conditions, rigid lesson planning is rarely effective. The responses of teachers in Tagum City show that adaptability is not simply a teaching preference but a necessity in ensuring that all learners can participate meaningfully. Through openness to change and sensitivity to individual learning styles, teachers turned potential classroom difficulties into opportunities for connection and growth.

Altogether, the responses underscore that flexibility is at the heart of effective English instruction in ALS. When teachers adapt to learners' unique circumstances, they create a classroom culture that values inclusion, patience, and progress at every level. This adaptability reflects not only the spirit of non-formal education but also the essence of communication itself: meeting learners where they are and guiding them toward where they can be.

Teachers in ALS classrooms thus understood that patience and empathy were not peripheral to instruction but essential tools for communication. By shaping spaces where learners felt supported and unafraid to participate, they encouraged hesitant individuals to take part actively, transforming the classroom into a place where English became approachable and confidence gradually took root.

Challenges of English Teachers in Using Communication Strategies for ALS Learners

Through a careful thematic analysis of the participants' responses on the difficulties they faced in applying communication strategies, three major themes emerged: (1) Resource Constraints in ALS Instruction, (2) Dealing with the Diversity of Learners, and (3) Managing Low Confidence of the Learners and Fear of Mistakes in Using English. These themes highlight the structural, instructional, and affective barriers that shaped the teaching of English in ALS classrooms in Tagum City, providing insight into the realities that teachers must navigate while striving to support their learners.

Experiencing Resource Constraints in ALS Instruction

The lack of adequate resources for instruction is a major challenge in ALS English teaching. Textbooks were either outdated or insufficient in number, and the modules provided often required significant contextualization to align with their learners' realities. Additionally, the limited supply of books and visuals, and limited internet access, further complicated lesson delivery, especially when sessions were irregular due to learners' attendance patterns.

Putra et al. (2023) argued that communication strategies enable teachers to sustain engagement even when exposure to English and materials are limited. Similarly, Milliner and Dimoski (2022) noted that such strategies help reduce misunderstandings and maintain continuity in language use when traditional learning resources are absent. In ALS contexts, where improvisation becomes a necessity rather than an option, teachers often adapt through visual aids, gestures, or real-life contextualization to compensate for the lack of formal materials (Mareza et al., 2021).

The challenge of insufficient resources has also been highlighted by Abad and Galleto (2020), who reported that the scarcity of instructional materials, facilities, and equipment hinders the effectiveness of ALS programs in certain divisions. Meanwhile, Besmonte (2023) observed that logistical difficulties and the lack of support structures make it harder for learners to consistently attend and benefit from the program. Essentially, the absence of reliable instructional resources not only constrained instructional quality but also contributed to inconsistent learner participation (Besmonte, 2023).

Meanwhile, Francisco and Buri (2024) emphasized that ALS teachers already face high workloads and diverse learner needs, and resource shortages only intensify these demands. Guiamalon et al. (2022) also highlighted that while improvisation demonstrates teacher resilience, it also underscores the systemic gaps that ALS facilitators must bridge on their own. Similarly, Abad and Galleto (2020) noted that limited instructional materials and facilities in ALS settings place additional pressure on teachers, often affecting the consistency and quality of learner engagement.

Addressing Challenges in Learner Diversity

Another challenge uncovered was the teaching of highly diverse groups of learners. Classes often include working students, single mothers, and Indigenous Peoples (IP) learners, each bringing distinct experiences and needs into the learning space. Teachers noted that this diversity translated into different levels of confidence and pace, making it difficult to deliver lessons in a way that supported everyone equally. Some learners required repeated explanations, while others quickly grasped the material and moved ahead. In several cases, differences in grade level and educational attainment created noticeable learning gaps that teachers had to bridge within the same session.

These challenges are consistent with the idea that communication strategies are meant to adapt to learners' needs when there are gaps in comprehension (Chen & Huang, 2024; Rahman & Isroyana, 2021). However, as Abdelkarim and Alhaj (2023) explain, such gaps often involve "problematicity," where learners recognize their difficulty in understanding but need significant teacher support to resolve it. For ALS learners with varied educational backgrounds, teachers cannot rely on a single strategy; instead, they must shift approaches to match different levels of proficiency and confidence.

The difficulty of addressing diversity in ALS classrooms has also been documented in earlier studies. Francisco and Buri (2024) identified diverse learner needs as one of the main challenges faced by ALS teachers, compounded by limited time and resources. Similarly, Guiamalon et al. (2022) pointed out that while ALS has been successful in providing access to education, there remains little focus on specific issues such as English instruction, which makes it even harder to serve learners who already come with uneven language skills. The responses of teachers in Tagum City confirm these challenges, showing that even within one class, learners may represent vastly different educational pathways and expectations.

At the same time, the need for repeated explanations and differentiated pacing illustrates why indirect and interactional strategies are critical in these contexts (Mareza et al., 2021; Zamani et al., 2022). Teachers often had to use clarification requests, paraphrasing, or simplified messages to ensure that those at lower proficiency levels could still participate. These efforts demonstrate how communication strategies become not only tools for language teaching but also mechanisms for inclusion in a highly diverse learning environment.

The teachers' responses show that learner diversity, while enriching, also creates constant challenges in communication. Facilitators are tasked with balancing multiple backgrounds, educational levels, and confidence levels within a single class. To cope, they depend on adaptive communication strategies that prioritize clarity, repetition, and negotiation of meaning, highlighting both the complexity and importance of teaching English in ALS.

Facing Low Confidence of the Learners and Fear of Mistakes in Using English

Many ALS learners struggled with low confidence when using English. Even when encouraged, some learners remained silent out of fear of making mistakes. Others hesitated to practice because they were afraid of being laughed at by their peers. In several cases, this fear was reinforced by past negative experiences in schooling, such as being scolded or punished for errors, which carried over into their present learning. These factors made students reluctant to take risks in communication, creating a barrier to language development.

This challenge reflects what Chan (2021) and Davlataliyeva (2021) describe as the conscious awareness of communication breakdowns, where learners know they are struggling but feel unable to resolve them. Instead of experimenting with strategies like circumlocution or asking for clarification, fear of failure keeps them from trying. In such cases, teachers often resorted to mixing English with Filipino or Bisaya, a practice aligned with achievement strategies that maintain communication despite gaps in language ability (Faerch & Kasper, 1980, as cited in Chen & Huang, 2024).

On the other hand, the hesitation to speak also connects to the idea of “affective barriers” in language learning. Smit et al. (2021) noted that communication strategies require not only cognitive skills but also the willingness to take risks in conversation. When learners fear embarrassment, their affective filter rises, limiting opportunities for practice. This is particularly evident in ALS, where learners come from diverse and sometimes disadvantaged backgrounds, carrying with them insecurities shaped by previous schooling experiences (Besmonte, 2023). Teachers' responses confirm that such barriers are not merely about language knowledge but about emotions tied to self-esteem and past encounters with education.

Moreover, Yu and Kaur (2024) observed that strategies such as confirming understanding or requesting clarification encourage learners to participate without the pressure of being perfect. However, for ALS learners, the persistence of fear meant that

teachers had to work harder to create safe spaces where mistakes were normalized. This connects with Abdelkarim and Alhaj's (2023) notion of problematicity, which highlights how learners' recognition of difficulties can either motivate strategy use or reinforce silence if not properly addressed.

Conclusions

Teaching in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) calls for empathy, adaptability, and a deep respect for the learners' diverse stories and circumstances. The experiences of ALS English teachers in Tagum City, as revealed in this study, illustrated how communication serves as the lifeblood of teaching in such a unique educational space. Their voices painted a picture of classrooms where connection, rather than correction, guides learning; where gestures, tone, and patience communicate as powerfully as words. These teachers exemplify how communication, when anchored in care and understanding, can bridge social and educational gaps and reignite learners' confidence to engage with English.

The findings showed that communication strategies such as code-switching, the use of the mother tongue, visual and non-verbal cues, and contextualized learning experiences play a crucial role in promoting comprehension and participation. By creating learner-centered and emotionally safe spaces, ALS teachers helped their students overcome fear and rediscover the joy of learning. What emerged was a learning environment that values understanding over perfection and dialogue over lecture—a reminder that language teaching, at its best, is deeply human.

At the same time, this study acknowledged the realities that ALS teachers continuously face: limited materials, irregular attendance, and diverse learner backgrounds that challenge traditional teaching methods. Despite these conditions, the teachers demonstrated remarkable creativity and resilience. They improvised lessons, used real-life examples, and adjusted their communication approaches to meet learners where they were. Their adaptability reflects the heart of ALS teaching, which can be pointed to meeting learners with compassion and flexibility rather than rigid standards.

Ultimately, this study affirms that communication is not merely a classroom strategy but the very essence of learning in the Alternative Learning System. When teachers communicate with empathy and adapt their methods to the realities of their learners, education becomes a tool for transformation. The responses of the English teachers in this study remind us that even within limited spaces and scarce resources, meaningful education thrives through connection, patience, and shared humanity.

Recommendations

This qualitative inquiry provided a contextual understanding of how English teachers in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) of Tagum City employed communication strategies to engage diverse learners. While the study generated meaningful insights into teachers' adaptive practices and challenges, its findings are

bounded by the perspectives of the selected participants and the specific educational setting of Tagum City. Therefore, the results cannot be generalized to all ALS programs or teachers in other divisions. In light of these limitations, several directions for future research are proposed.

First, future studies may expand the scope of inquiry by involving a larger number of ALS teachers from other divisions or regions. Moreover, conducting comparative studies across urban and rural contexts, or among different provinces, may also reveal how geographical, cultural, and institutional differences influence the communication strategies employed in ALS classrooms. Such an expanded dataset could provide a broader understanding of how teachers adapt language, materials, and methods to varying learner populations and resource conditions.

Second, subsequent research may explore the perspectives of other stakeholders in the ALS learning ecosystem. For instance, examining the experiences of ALS learners themselves could provide valuable insights into how they perceive teachers' communication strategies and how these affect their motivation, comprehension, and confidence in using English. Similarly, the views of education program specialists, learning facilitators, or administrators could highlight institutional factors that shape teachers' communicative practices. Triangulating these viewpoints could strengthen the depth and validity of future findings.

Next, researchers may consider employing mixed-methods designs to complement the qualitative insights gained from this study. Quantitative instruments could be developed to measure specific outcomes of communication strategies, such as learner confidence, engagement, or comprehension levels. Combining narrative and numerical evidence may lead to stronger empirical foundations for designing teacher training and policy interventions in ALS. Longitudinal research may also be valuable to trace how communication strategies evolve over time as teachers gain more experience or adapt to changing learner profiles.

Additionally, future researchers could focus on specific communication approaches identified in this study, such as code-switching, peer learning, or contextualized instruction, and assess their impact on learners' language proficiency and participation. Classroom-based case studies or micro-level analyses of teacher–learner interactions could shed light on the subtle ways teachers construct meaning and manage dialogue in multilingual settings. This would deepen understanding of communicative competence not only as a teaching skill but also as a dynamic interaction shaped by culture, confidence, and learner diversity.

Lastly, it is recommended that future research examine how teacher preparation and professional development programs can better integrate communication strategies suited for non-formal education contexts like ALS. Exploring the link between teacher training, reflective practice, and classroom communication could inform curriculum design for future ALS facilitators. Through these future studies, scholars, academicians, and ALS practitioners can build upon the present findings to enhance communicative strategies,

promote inclusive learning, and strengthen the delivery of English instruction in the Alternative Learning System.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers conducted this study in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were handled in accordance with Data Privacy regulations. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process. The researcher affirms that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the findings were interpreted without bias. The results of this research were used solely for academic purposes. Furthermore, any use of artificial intelligence tools in the preparation of this study has been fully disclosed to ensure transparency.

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